

PARADIGMS OF APPLICATION OF BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE IN SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES IN SERBIA

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Abstract

Today's times bring new and rapid changes in the business environment every day, to which small and medium-sized enterprises should adapt as soon as possible, often on the fly. With the development of new information technologies of artificial and business intelligence in the 20th and 21st centuries, everything becomes dependent on the availability of information and thus on investments in innovations and new technologies, not only in technological but also in business development. In the theoretical part of the research, based on the results of eminent world authors in this field, the concepts, terms, functions and methods of business intelligence are explained, from the aspect of business optimization and improvement of business decision-making. In this regard, we investigate the theoretical basis of business intelligence and a possible practical demonstration of the implementation of these systems in SMEs in Serbia. The aim of the research is a qualitative, studious analysis of the advantages and disadvantages, as well as the possibilities of applying new business intelligence technologies and approaches in SME operations in Serbia, in the conditions of the global economic crisis and recession, with the aim of optimizing and improving operations, i.e. survival in the increasingly open world market. The empirical part will present the results of research conducted in practice, through the classification and statistical performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in Serbia, then the areas in which the application of business intelligence has yielded the best results will be presented, and finally the effects of its application in specific companies in Serbia. In this context, it can be said that for the purposes of the research, the ever-present growing need for the use of business intelligence methods, techniques and tools from the aspect of improving and optimizing company operations, as well as computer-supported methods and methodologies for decision-making in companies, has been studiously analyzed. The theoretical and practical parts of the work are interconnected and in constant interaction.

Keywords: Small and medium enterprises, business intelligence, artificial intelligence.

Field: Technical and technological sciences

1. INTRODUCTION

Companies in Serbia today operate in an extremely uncertain and volatile environment with an extremely high level of uncertainty and the inability to predict the future. The latest research shows that employers in Serbia are often fighting the crisis by laying off workers and freezing wages[7]. In this regard, there are also certain differences between the size of business entities, as the data shows that compared to the small and medium-sized enterprise sector (hereinafter referred to as SMEs), large companies record productivity at a significantly higher level (in 2021 by 58.8%, in 2022 by 53.6% and in 2023 by 59.5% above the SME average). Research in practice shows that SMEs are under increasing pressure to survive in an increasingly

competitive market and in this sense they find a solution in the application of new sophisticated technologies such as artificial and business intelligence, although until recently this was characteristic of large companies[11]. Representative research in the world shows that almost half of the respondents (47%) stated that their company had already laid off workers, while 46% stated that their salaries had been frozen. Furthermore, 36% of the respondents stated that the companies where they work had frozen financing for new projects, 33% that salaries had been reduced, while 32% of the respondents stated that they had cut education costs [2]. In this context, research indicates the importance and crucial importance of analyzing business data and information.

2. THEORETICAL BASICS OF SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES

Business practice in the world shows that micro, small and medium-sized enterprises are considered one of the leading forces of economic development because they represent the most efficient segment of the economy in almost all countries of the world. The results of the Republic of Serbia's Statistical Office indicate the importance and significance of small and medium-sized enterprises in Serbia, illustrating this with basic indicators - that these enterprises account for 99.8% of the total number of enterprises in the non-financial sector[24]. In this context, it is estimated that the total economic activity in the Republic of Serbia in 2025, measured by the real movement of gross domestic product (GDP), recorded a growth of 2.0% compared to 2024. Similar data are in the world where the largest number of enterprises registered in the territory of the European Union are small and medium-sized enterprises, it is estimated that 99% of enterprises, out of over 200 million enterprises, 93% of which are the smallest, so-called

micro-enterprises, which have up to ten employees. Precise data according to the latest data from the Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia show that out of a total of 110,287 enterprises in the Republic of Serbia, in 2023 there were: 94,078 micro (85.3 percent), 12,613 small (11.4 percent), 2,953 medium (2.7 percent) and 643 large enterprises (0.6 percent). According to available data, more than 940,000 workers are employed in SMEs, which is 67.2% of the total number of employees in the non-financial sector and 43.2% of the total number of employees[24]. One of the most appropriate ways to create a competitive advantage for SMEs in Serbia, in the current conditions of the global economic crisis and recession, is the concept of business intelligence[12]. In this regard, the current application of business intelligence methods, techniques and tools is justified, i.e. the demand for accurate, timely and useful information in SMEs is extremely high[13]. The following figure 1 shows statistics of companies in the Republic of Serbia.

Table 1. Classification of companies by size in Serbia 2

As can be seen, whether they are complete or customized business intelligence solutions, they bring corresponding improvements in market positioning and competitiveness, as well as better, new ways of managing information and knowledge.

3. THEORETICAL BASIS OF BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE

The relevant literature states that business intelligence is the ability of an organization to understand and use data to improve its operations or to use existing data, information, and knowledge within the company [21]. This is supported by the opinions of Turban et al (2021), who emphasize that business intelligence is "an umbrella term that combines and defines tools, databases, analytical tools, applications, and methodologies"[26]. Similarly, Kimball and Ross define business intelligence as an umbrella term to describe "concepts and methods for improving business decision-making with the help of evidence-based support systems"[17]. However, practical results show that for the application of business intelligence to be effective, appropriate IT knowledge and competencies are necessary. In this context, Chao and Chandra (2012) conducted a survey of 217 small manufacturers and financial services organizations in the USA and found that the level of IT knowledge of the owners is a key predictor of IT strategic positioning, as well as the adoption of business intelligence[3]. The literature states that the goal of in-

roducing business intelligence is to support and improve business decision-making processes in companies [4]. In essence, business intelligence is the process of collecting data and information that, after appropriate processing, becomes knowledge[25]. In general, it can be said that business intelligence is a general term that describes the use of internal and external sources of information in companies, in a way that facilitates making better decisions[17]. Based on the above, the conclusion is that business intelligence produces knowledge that is the basis for optimizing and improving business and making better business decisions. The definition presented by Gartner emphasizes that this is a term that includes applications, infrastructure, which enable analysis and access to information in order to improve and optimize business, processes, decisions and performance[14]. One of the most complete definitions of business intelligence can be found on the IBM website: "Business intelligence is the collection, management, analysis and sharing of information to gain insights that can be used to make better decisions. The famous author Howson (2013) defines business intelligence as a technology that enables people from all levels of the enterprise and business systems to access, interact and process data for business management, in order to improve their work, discover new opportunities and work more efficiently[15]. In this regard, it can be said that business intelligence is the process of collect-

ing significant internal and external data and transforming it into information and useful new knowledge needed by SMEs to improve their business and make business decisions[1]. Based on the evolution of the relevant literature, the following can be distinguished as the main tools and techniques of business intelligence:

- ✓ Data warehouses - data storage in a way that enables the satisfaction of numerous analytical needs.
- ✓ ETL tools (eng. Extraction, Transformation, Load) - tools for extracting and normalizing data. Data sources reside in or out of numerous databases, and in both cases the data must be recognized as relevant and extracted from its existing location into the system for transfer or transformation.
- ✓ OLAP (eng. On-line Analytical Processing) - enable data in the warehouse to be analyzed in multiple dimensions, which expands the metrics by which users value information.
- ✓ Data mining (eng. Data Mining) - an unconventional way of finding hidden patterns or rules in large data sets that can be of great advantage and importance.
- ✓ Business reporting - visualization via business portals, balanced scorecards, digital dashboards.
- ✓ Monitoring of basic performance indicators - KPI (eng. Key Performance Indicators)
- ✓ Monitoring of business activities - BPM (eng. Business Process Management)

Eminent authors define a data warehouse as a subjectively oriented, integrated, time-varying, non-normalized and consistent set of data for analytical decision support [27]. The next factor is the so-called. ETL process, which is one of the most complex and commonly used data preparation techniques for business intelligence purposes. The goal of the ETL process is to select, clean and integrate data from various sources into the data warehouse, so this process is the basis of the business intelligence process. On average, 70% of the total time spent on the implementation of a business intelligence system is spent on the ETL process itself [17], with the cause of the problem most often being poor quality of the data source, which unequivocally indicates the importance of the quality of business data and information. This is confirmed by the authors who state that the emphasis of the ETL process consists of sub-selection, cleaning, unification and delivery of data in a dimensional data model. The next factor is the so-called. OLAP tools, the use of which in data warehouses is in the function of more transparent and clear information. However, the results in practice show that despite this, it is noticeable that due to the large amount of data, business analysts work very hard, slowly and often inefficiently. It is estimated that today companies receive huge amounts of business data from internal and external sources, of which they barely manage to use about 5 to 10%. This is supported by the latest research by well-known authors, which indicates that a typical company has 90% of the necessary data and information, necessary for efficient business operations, but effectively uses only 10% of the available data and

information[19][20]. In this direction, the role and importance of tools for discovering knowledge in data are reflected, which instead of analysts automatically analyze data and display results. Data mining tools are essentially a kind of alternative in the search for business information, where the amount of input data is enormous, and the necessary business information is hidden and very difficult to access. This is exactly what a quality business intelligence system will provide to the manager, and this can be achieved if the data obtained from such systems is used in the best possible way. However, the results in practice show that although business intelligence is often mentioned in SMEs in Serbia today, unfortunately the business discipline is still used negligibly little.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methods used in this research work include the use of standard scientific methods such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, description, induction and deduction, compilation, and methods of proof. In this context, it can be said that a research framework was applied that combines different research methods, thus including quantitative and qualitative research methods [23].

5. RESULTS

Another in a series of studies, which indicates the enormous growth of the amount of data, is a study conducted by Gartner, where 47% of respondents qualified the growth of business data among the three biggest challenges of modern management[14]. The results of the study show that the application of advanced techniques; ETL, OLAP, DM, DW, and the introduction of intelligent information systems in SMEs raises business to a higher level, which enables efficient monitoring of business processes. The problems of managers in companies are noticeable and significant because, according to research, about 54% of business users cannot find the necessary information, 43% are not sure whether the information they receive is accurate, while 77% claim that bad decisions are made solely due to a lack of information. According to the results of representative research by individual authors Kielstra, the most important attributes of information needed for decision-making are: quality (65%), completeness (18%), timeliness (13%), and price (5%) [16]. The well-known expert Eppler emphasizes that for SMEs today the quality of information is crucial, not the quantity. An example from practice shows that thanks to the successful implementation of OLAP functionality in the analyzed company "Lipovica", the management came to the conclusion that in a period of 5 years it is possible to expand capacities by 24% and redistribute planting and cutting material, which would bring a total profit of 48% compared to the current period [8]. This is complemented by the opinions that can be seen in the following figure 2 that company managers clearly want to shift their focus from data collection to the use of data in business optimization and more efficient business decision-making.

Fig. 2. The main pressures for the use of business intelligence in SME 2

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Research indicates that the best business intelligence model in times of economic crisis and recession is one that will help SMEs achieve a competitive advantage, while being inexpensive[9]. For this purpose, OSBI (Open Source Business Intelligence) has been increasingly discussed recently. Implementation projects, or rather the introduction of business intelligence into companies, are extremely demanding and complex. However, despite the fact that the latest research in the world indicates that, for example, out of 43 American companies that participated in the research, 46% achieved 100% or less return on investment, 34% between 101% and 1000%, and 20% around 1001% and more, they are still not applied to the necessary and sufficient extent in SMEs in Serbia. It is important to note that not all data warehouses are suitable for business intelligence, just as not all business intelligence applications require data warehouses[10]. However, according to some surveys, more than 90% of larger and successful companies in Europe use some form of data storage and business intelligence, while in Serbia it is still less than 10%. However, in practice, there are certain obstacles to the widespread use of business intelligence, such as research cited by Davenport and Ronanki (2018), which emphasizes that despite the recognized benefits, the lack of professional knowledge and trust in intelligent systems remain the most common obstacles to the application of business or artificial

intelligence in business, or in the process of business decision-making and management with the aim of improving business[6]. Considering that according to research, more than 70% end either with deadlines being exceeded or inefficient, the authors Olszak and Ziembra (2012) consider the so-called critical success factors for establishing business intelligence in SMEs, which highlight common features of obstacles such as: financial, organizational-cultural and IT barriers within the company[22]. If the above figures are presented as a payback period for the invested funds, the situation is as follows: 49% of companies recovered the funds invested in a business intelligence project in one year or less, 32% in a period of one to three years, 19% in three or more years. The results of research in the world indicate that a typical business intelligence project has an average return of over 430%. According to available data, this year, according to the readiness index for the implementation of business or artificial intelligence, Serbia ranked 39th out of a total of 195 assessed economies worldwide, which places it among the top 20 percent of the most prepared economies at the global level. Research shows that business intelligence functionally affects the improvement of the operations of small and medium-sized business systems, forming a positive attitude towards the effects of the application of intelligent systems for decision support in the company (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. The main pressures for the use of business intelligence in SME 2

The largest application of business intelligence in Serbia was recorded in the information, communication

and professional sectors, where 62% of companies use

business or artificial intelligence [28]. According to Eurostat data, only 8% of companies in Europe used business or artificial intelligence in their operations in 2023, and Serbia is only at an estimated 2% of applications.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The research shows that SMEs account for over 50 percent of Serbia's exports, which further indicates the relevance and importance of this research. The research results indicate that the use of business intelligence will result in business success only if business intelligence users regularly develop business and decision-making processes, recognize their needs, help in their modeling and monitor the completion of the project, as well as actively participate in the implementation of new business intelligence components. In this regard, access to information and its processing into relevant knowledge is of great importance for a company of any size. The basic concept of the research is guided by the idea that by synthesizing modern IT methods and techniques: ETL, OLAP, DW and Data Mining through the practical application of business intelligence concepts, tools and techniques, a new high-quality information system for SMEs can be developed that improves work at the operational level, and primarily makes it easier for top management to make the right business decisions important for the survival and development of SMEs in Serbia. To successfully adapt to the ever-changing market, SMEs must understand what changes are taking place and how this can affect their business. The results of thorough research indicate that the greatest contribution to business efficiency is quick insight into a large amount of data and shortening the time to access information. In last year's report, Serbia ranked 57th in terms of readiness for the implementation of business intelligence, or artificial intelligence. The research shows that the benefits of implementing a business intelligence project include centralized knowledge, improved decision-making processes, systematization and recognition of opportunities, better implementation of business processes, greater productivity and competitiveness.

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